

Environmental Awareness in Sanskrit Literature

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The environment, a delicate reciprocity of ecosystem not only gives us vital resources but also sustains our lives. The modern concept of environmental science came into light as a substantive, active field of scientific investigation in the 1960s only. In 1970s, to analyze the complex environmental problems, it is considered as a multi-disciplinary approach, requiring specific protocols of investigation by increasing public awareness regarding environmental issues. In fact, every generations of human being have the right to have the benefit from the past generation and also have the obligation to preserve cultural and natural heritage. So, proper care should be taken to preserve the natural resources and to save the environment. In ancient India, people were very much conscious for the protection of environment and there was a very cordial relationship between human and environment. The evidences of this can be noticed in different scriptures like Vedas, epics, Purânas and allied literature. Different natural resources like the earth, flora and fauna have got a special position in the works of Sanskrit literature, which are accepted as earliest written documents of Indian civilization. As like the treatises, the people of antiquity also were very much concerned about the purity of air and water. The awareness shown by Indic people for environment before 5000 thousand years were akin with modern concepts. If awareness activities can be continued, we can take help from earliest documents and apply those in today's circumstances to make a well being space.

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